

THE IMPORTANCE OF NUTRITION IN VARIOUS SPORTS

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Abstract. *The diet of an athlete is the same as the diet of healthy children and adolescents. Providing the body with the necessary amount of energy, plastic (construction) and biologically active substances. Eating is considered as an active factor, that is, maintaining health, preventing diseases, ensuring the natural growth and development process, and expanding the limits of adaptation to constant physical loads. Inadequate supply of nutrients to the body can lead to harm to health, inability to resist harmful factors in the environment, deterioration of mental and physical capacity for work.*

Keywords: *protein, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals*

The demand for high achievements in modern sports makes it important for a child to play sports from the age of 3-4. Therefore, when children are given to sports sections to practice different sports, he works hard and carries excessive loads. Many parents and coaches neglect proper nutrition, taking into account age, health, type of sport, period of training and competition, and time of rest, in order to ensure proper adaptation of children and adolescents to these processes. However, not all coaches and athletes have proper nutritional information, and due to a lack of knowledge in this area, they incorrectly determine the nutritional regimen. It is not correct to eat too much of one type of food product, which does not help to achieve high sports results.

According to the oral survey, 55% of children aged 7 to 10 eat 3 times a day, children aged 11 to 13 and 14 to 16 eat 3–4 times a day; 6% of children eat 5 times a day. 95% of children and teenagers eat breakfast, and for lunch they mostly take sandwiches, buns, cakes from the buffet; high school students eat fast food and sweet black tea; in the evening, all children eat at home. According to the studies, 11% of children eat hot food once a day, 70% of children eat 2 meals a day, and 17% of participants eat hot food 3 times a day. No difference was observed between girls and boys in the comparative assessment of food intake.

When analyzing the supply of basic food products of the studied children, it was observed that some food products were in short supply due to the uncoordinated main nutrition of sports students aged 7–10, 11–13 and 14–16 years and irrationality of new food products. According to questionnaires, bread, cereal and confectionery products are mainly included in the diet. Dietary fiber was 90% when the daily diet did not meet the nutritional standards for fresh vegetables and fruits. (see tables).

Composition of food in the diet of 7-10-year-old chess and drafts children

Food name	Hygiene standard , g	Actual content			
		Winter-spring season		Summer-autumn season	
		abs ., g	to % norm	abs ., g	to % norm
Bread and bakery products	259	363	140.2	336	129.7

Milk and milk products	505	361	71.5	337	66.7
Meat and meat products	125	97	77.6	89	71.2
Fish and seafood	30	9	30.0	6	20.0
Vegetable oils	15	13	86.7	11	73.3
Animal fats	15	14	93.3	10	66.7
Sugar and confectionery products	65	59	90.8	55	84.6
Potatoes	130	110	84.6	106	81.5
Vegetables	300	280	93.3	320	106.7
Fruits and berries	210	174	82.9	245	116.7
Eggs (units)	0.8	0.64	80.0	0.42	52.5

A healthy child is the main problem of the near and long future of any country, because all opportunities (both economic and creative), all social and economic development prospects, a high standard of living, science and culture - all this is the level of health of children, their ability to physical and mental work. is the effect of the

The diet of young athletes is based on the concept of coordinated and proper nutrition, with the adaptation of physical requirements. The following principles are taken into account when organizing the rational nutrition of athletes: compliance of the ration power with the average daily power consumption, depending on age, gender, type and speed of physical exertion; coordination of the diet in terms of basic nutrients (proteins, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins and minerals); depending on the specific pedagogical tasks, choosing a sufficient type of nutrition (products, nutrients and their combinations) to ensure different directions of the diet (protein, carbohydrate, protein-carbohydrate) in training aimed at individual preparation of athletes for competitions; distributing the ration throughout the day according to the type and order of training and competitions. The nutrition of children involved in sports should not only be related to the need for effective training and achieving high sports performance, but should also meet the need for nutrients and energy that ensure the growth and development of children and adolescents. Due to increased sweating and fluid flow during active physical exertion, water-salt exchange is disturbed, as a result of which microelements, primarily sodium and potassium, change the functional state of the heart-blood, nervous-muscular system. It is important to take into account the type of sport that a young athlete is engaged in, the duration of training, when organizing the procedure for drinking water. Sports drinks are recommended for those who practice long-term sports. It is considered necessary for athletes to drink fluids before, during and after training. The nutrition of children involved in sports should meet the need for nutrients and energy, which support the child's continuous growth and development, not only for the effective training process and high sports performance. Rational organization of meals helps in the process of strengthening health, improving sports ability, recovery and adaptation to physical loads.

CONCLUSION.

It is important that there are more young athletes in many sports now . Physically mature adolescents often engage in daily exercise regularly during adolescence, a period of high motivational power. But in order to achieve good results in training and competitions, it is

necessary to start the activity before the period of sexual maturity. The diets of children and adolescents who play sports are often deficient in essential nutrients and vitamins for energy. When working with children, nutritionists often use the standards recommended for adults. However, due to physical loads, physiological changes and rapid growth during sports, the child's body needs additional energy. Professionals working with young athletes face great difficulties in defining the concept of "norms".

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